

Intuitionistic Fuzzy Implicative Ideals with Thresholds (λ, μ) of BCI-Algebras

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Abstract : The aim of this paper is to introduce the notion of intuitionistic fuzzy implicative ideals with thresholds (λ, μ) of BCI-algebras and to investigate its properties and characterizations.

Keywords : BCI-algebra, intuitionistic fuzzy set, intuitionistic fuzzy ideal with thresholds (λ, μ) , intuitionistic fuzzy implicative ideal with thresholds (λ, μ) .

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